

FREQUENCY OF CAUSES OF NON-TRAUMATIC COMPRESSIVE MYELOPATHY ON MRI IN PATIENTS WITH PARAPLEGIA / QUADRIPLEGIA

Dr. Sanjna¹, Professor Shaista Shaukat², Dr. Abdul Samad³, Dr. Piriha Nisar⁴,
Dr. Varsha⁵, Sumera Tabassum⁶

^{1,3,4,5}Mbbs, Fcps-Ii Postgraduate Trainee Fcps-Ii Postgraduate Trainee Jpmc Karachi

²Mbbs, Fcps, Edir, C.H.P.E Professor Jpmc Karachi

⁶Mbbs, Fcps, Edir, C.H.P.E Associate Professor Jpmc Karachi

¹sanjanamotwani99@gmail.com, ²sktshaista@gmail.com, ³drshaikhsamad@gmail.com,
⁴sirahnisar9197@gmail.com, ⁵varsha.sachdev16@yahoo.com, ⁶sumert57f@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17309641>

Keywords

Non-Traumatic Compressive
Myelopathy, Spinal Cord
Compression, Paraplegia,
Quadriplegia, MRI, Etiology

Article History

Received: 10 February 2025

Accepted: 28 March 2025

Published: 14 April 2025

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Corresponding Author: *
Dr. Sanjna

Abstract

OBJECTIVE

To determine the frequency and etiological spectrum of non-traumatic compressive myelopathy (NTCM) in adult patients presenting with paraplegia or quadriplegia, using MRI findings as the diagnostic standard at a tertiary care center in Pakistan.

METHODOLOGY

This cross-sectional descriptive investigation was executed in the Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Centre, Karachi. One hundred and fifteen participants were included who had clinically validated cases of paraplegia or quadriplegia, of non-traumatic etiology. Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) was employed to identify and categorize the etiologies of non-traumatic compressive myelopathy. The data were subjected to analysis utilizing SPSS version 26.0, with statistical significance established at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

A total of 115 patients were evaluated, with a mean age of 45.69 ± 17.06 years. The patient population consisted of 64 males (55.7%) and 51 females (44.3%). Tumors were the most common cause (25.2%), followed by degenerative diseases (15.7%), infections (8.7%), and other pathologies (50.4%). No statistically significant differences were observed between paraplegic and quadriplegic patients in terms of age ($p = 0.778$), gender ($p = 0.464$), or etiology ($p > 0.05$).

CONCLUSION

The research emphasizes that non-traumatic compressive myelopathy is characterized by an etiological spectrum in which tumors comprise the most common cause, followed by degenerative and infectious pathology. MRI was imperative to proper diagnosis. There was no significant difference between paraplegic and quadriplegic groups in the etiological distribution, and thus the importance of early imaging and etiological assessment in all patients presenting with non-traumatic spinal cord dysfunction.

INTRODUCTION

Myelopathy refers to any neurological deficit related to the spinal cord [1]. The causes can be either traumatic or non-traumatic. Non-traumatic compressive myelopathy (NTCM) is a significant but underreported cause of paralysis, encompassing a wide range of etiologies that cause compressive myelopathy and severe disability. These include neoplastic, vascular, mechanical, infectious, and degenerative pathologies. In developed countries, tumors, whether primary or metastatic, are the most common cause of NTCM, followed by age-related conditions such as degenerative disc disease [2]. In contrast, tuberculosis is the most common cause in developing countries, driven by factors such as poverty, overpopulation, and malnutrition [3]. However, in recent decades, there has been a resurgence of tuberculosis in developed countries, affecting not only the lungs but also extra-pulmonary sites like the vertebral column [4]. This resurgence can largely be attributed to dynamic immigration patterns that have brought individuals from regions where tuberculosis is endemic [1,5,6].

Diagnosing the causes of NTCM can be challenging due to varying clinical presentations. Imaging, combined with clinical and laboratory testing, is used for diagnosis, with MRI being the gold standard for detecting cord compression, boasting an overall accuracy of 95% [7]. Plain computerized tomography (CT) and plain X-rays of the cervical spine are generally not helpful, though they can reveal fractures, stenosis due to osteophytes, and cervical spinal instability [8]. CT myelography is an option for patient's intolerant of closed spaces or unable to undergo MRI [9]. MRI with and without gadolinium outperforms CT myelography in diagnosing tumors, inflammation, demyelination, spondylosis, infection, ischemia, syringomyelia, and other spinal conditions. Due to the limited upper extremity signs and symptoms in cervical myelopathy patients, imaging often includes both the cervical and thoracic spine. For patients with suspected arteriovenous malformations or spinal cord ischemia, MR angiography or conventional trans-femoral angiography is employed to confirm the diagnosis, map the blood supply, and plan potential surgical interventions [10,11]. Most studies focus on traumatic spinal cord injury [3,12], but non-

traumatic compressive myelopathy accounts for a surprisingly large portion (up to 50%) of SCI cases admitted for rehabilitation [1]. The incidence and etiology of NTCM vary widely depending on geographic and demographic factors. Understanding the frequency and causes of NTCM is crucial for clinicians to develop effective treatment protocols. In Pakistan, there is a paucity of data on the prevalence and causes of NTCM. Since NTCM can result from various pathologies such as spinal tumors, infections, or degenerative diseases, a detailed analysis will provide insights into the predominant causes in the local population, which may differ from global trends due to genetic, environmental, and healthcare system differences.

METHODOLOGY

This cross-sectional descriptive investigation was undertaken in the Department of Radiology at Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Centre, Karachi, aiming to evaluate the underlying causes of non-traumatic compressive myelopathy (NTCM) in patients presenting with paraplegia or quadriplegia. A total of 115 cases were studied. Sample size was calculated using the WHO Open Epi Sample Size calculator, keeping the prevalence of non-traumatic compressive myelopathy as (88%)¹⁴, with a margin of error of 5% and a confidence interval of 95%. Patients were enrolled using non-probability consecutive sampling. Eligible participants included adults aged 18 years or above of any gender, with clinically confirmed paraplegia or quadriplegia of non-traumatic origin, who had undergone MRI. Non-traumatic compressive myelopathy was defined as spinal cord compression by non-traumatic lesions such as tumors, degenerative disorders, infections, or other pathological causes, and was confirmed through characteristic clinical findings—such as progressive motor weakness, sensory deficits, or sphincter dysfunction—correlated with MRI results. Paraplegia was defined as loss of motor and/or sensory function in the lower limbs due to thoracic or lower spinal cord involvement, while quadriplegia was defined as similar dysfunction affecting all four limbs due to cervical spinal

involvement. Patients were excluded if they had traumatic spinal injuries, non-compressive myelopathies, incomplete clinical records, or contraindications to MRI. After obtaining approval from the institutional review board, informed written consent was taken from all participants. A structured proforma was used for data collection, recording demographics, clinical history, and MRI findings. All MRIs were interpreted by a senior radiologist with at least five years of experience, who identified and categorized the causes of NTCM into major groups: neoplastic (e.g., intramedullary, intradural-extramedullary, and extradural tumors), degenerative (e.g., disc herniation, spondylosis, osteophytes),

RESULTS

The study included 115 participants with a mean age of 45.69 ± 17.06 years (95% CI: 42.54–48.84) and a mean symptom duration of 32.70 ± 16.95 months (95% CI: 29.57–35.84). Among them, 64 (55.7%) were male and 51 (44.3%) were female. In terms of residential status, 63 (54.8%) participants resided in urban areas, while 52 (45.2%) were from rural areas. Regarding the clinical course, 36 (31.3%) presented with progressive disease, 42 (36.5%) had a stable course, and 37 (32.2%) experienced a recurrent course. Sphincter impairment was noted in several forms: urinary incontinence in 32 (27.8%), fecal incontinence in 34 (29.6%), constipation in 24 (20.9%), and double sphincter impairment in 25 (21.7%). Sensory level assessment showed that 44 (38.3%) participants had absent sensory level, 32 (27.8%) had thoracic involvement, and 39 (33.9%) had cervical involvement (TABLE I).

Among the 115 cases of non-traumatic compressive myelopathy (NTCM), etiological analysis revealed a diverse distribution of underlying causes. Tumors accounted for 29 cases, with metastatic lesions being the most frequent (31.0%), followed by extradural masses (27.6%), intradural-extramedullary tumors (20.7%), and intramedullary tumors (20.7%). Degenerative diseases were observed in 18 patients, predominantly due to herniated discs (44.4%), osteophytes (27.8%), and spondylosis (27.8%).

infectious (e.g., tuberculous spondylitis, epidural abscesses), and other pathologies such as cysts, hematomas, or vascular anomalies. Data was anonymized and stored securely to maintain confidentiality. Statistical analysis was done on IBM SPSS version 26.0. The descriptive statistics were also used to present a summary of the continuous variables (mean + standard deviation) and categorical variables (frequencies and percentages). The tests of association between variables were performed with chi-square test and p-value under 0.05 was treated as statistically significant.

Infections were identified in 10 patients, of which tuberculous spondylitis was the leading cause (70.0%), followed by epidural abscesses (30.0%). The largest category, other pathologies, comprised 58 cases, with notable contributions from multiple sclerosis (19.0%), vertebral fractures (15.5%), arteriovenous malformations (13.8%), spinal cord ischemia (12.1%), spinal cysts (10.3%), hematomas (8.6%), spinal instability (8.6%), syringomyelia (6.9%), and transverse myelitis (5.2%) (TABLE II).

In the comparison of patient characteristics and etiological categories between paraplegic (n=54) and quadriplegic (n=61) patients, no statistically significant differences were observed across demographic or clinical variables. The mean age of paraplegic patients was 46.17 ± 17.65 years compared to 45.26 ± 16.65 years in quadriplegic patients ($p = 0.778$). The mean duration of symptoms was also similar, with 31.15 ± 16.95 months in paraplegics and 34.08 ± 16.97 months in quadriplegics ($p = 0.357$). Gender distribution did not differ significantly, with males comprising 59.3% of paraplegics and 52.5% of quadriplegics ($p = 0.464$). Regarding etiological categories, tumors were present in 27.8% of paraplegic patients and 23.0% of quadriplegic patients, degenerative diseases in 13.0% and 18.0%, infections in 11.1% and 6.6%, and other pathologies in 48.1% and 52.5%, respectively, with no significant differences between the two groups (all $p > 0.05$) (TABLE III).

Table I: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Study Participants (n=115)

Mean ± Standard Deviation	95% Confidence Interval
Age in years = 45.69 ± 17.06	42.54–48.84

Duration of Symptoms in months = 32.70 ± 16.95		29.57---35.84
n (%)		
Gender	Male	64 (55.7)
	Female	51 (44.3)
Residential Status	Urban	63 (54.8)
	Rural	52 (45.2)
Clinical Course	Progressive	36 (31.3)
	Stable	42 (36.5)
	Recurrent	37 (32.2)
Sphincter Impairment	Urinary Incontinence	32 (27.8)
	Fecal Incontinence	34 (29.6)
	Constipation	24 (20.9)
	Double Sphincter Impairment	25 (21.7)
Sensory Level	Absent	44 (38.3)
	Thoracic	32 (27.8)
	Cervical	39 (33.9)

Table II: Distribution of Causes of Non-Traumatic Compressive Myelopathy According to Etiological Categories (n=115)

Causes of NTCM	Etiological Categories			
	Tumors (n=29)	Degenerative Diseases (n=18)	Infections (n=10)	Other Pathologies (n=58)
AV malformation	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	8 (13.8)
Epidural abscess	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (30.0)	0 (0.0)
Extradural mass	8 (27.6)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
Hematoma	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	5 (8.6)
Herniated disc	0 (0.0)	8 (44.4)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
Intradural-extramedullary tumor	6 (20.7)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
Intramedullary tumor	6 (20.7)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
Metastatic lesion	9 (31.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
Multiple sclerosis	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	11 (19.0)
Osteophytes	0 (0.0)	5 (27.8)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
Spinal cord ischemia	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	7 (12.1)
Spinal cyst	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	6 (10.3)
Spinal instability	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	5 (8.6)
Spondylosis	0 (0.0)	5 (27.8)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
Syringomyelia	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	4 (6.9)
Transverse myelitis	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (5.2)
Tuberculous spondylitis	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	7 (70.0)	0 (0.0)

Vertebral fracture	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	9 (15.5)
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Table III: Comparison of Patient Characteristics and Etiological Categories Between Paraplegic and Quadriplegic Patients (n=115)

Patient Characteristics & Etiological Categories		Patient Status		P-Value
		Paraplegic (n=54)	Quadriplegic (n=61)	
Age in years		46.17 ± 17.65	45.26 ± 16.65	0.778
Duration of Symptoms in months		31.15 ± 16.95	34.08 ± 16.97	0.357
Gender	Male	32 (59.3)	32 (52.5)	0.464
	Female	22 (40.7)	29 (47.5)	
Etiological Categories	Tumors	15 (27.8)	14 (23.0)	0.677
	Degenerative Diseases	7 (13.0)	11 (18.0)	
	Infections	6 (11.1)	4 (6.6)	
	Other Pathologies	26 (48.1)	32 (52.5)	

Applied independent t-test and Chi -Square test

DISCUSSION

This study investigates the etiological distribution of non-traumatic compressive myelopathy (NTCM) in a Pakistani tertiary care center. The findings emphasize the diversity of underlying causes and reinforce the importance of timely diagnosis and advanced imaging, particularly MRI.

Among the 115 patients studied, tumors were responsible for 25% of cases, with metastatic lesions being the most common. This observation is consistent with data from Spain, where tumors were the predominant cause of NTCM over a 36-year period [2]. Similarly, Abrahm described malignant spinal cord compression, especially from metastases, as a key concern in cancer care [7]. Lekoubou Looti et al. reported an even higher prevalence of neoplastic causes in Cameroon [14], suggesting variability based on cancer incidence and access to oncology services.

Degenerative spinal diseases such as disc herniation and spondylosis accounted for 15.7% of cases. While lower than in some developed nations, this finding aligns with studies from Japan and South Korea,

where cervical spondylotic myelopathy has become the leading cause of spinal dysfunction in aging populations [15,16]. Our comparatively lower rates may reflect the younger age of presentation in our cohort or underdiagnosis due to limited screening and delayed access to MRI.

Infectious causes, particularly tuberculous spondylitis, constituted 8.7% of our sample. Spinal tuberculosis was the leading infectious cause, which corresponds with findings from Nigeria and India, where TB remains a major contributor to spinal pathology due to persistent socio-economic challenges [3,13,17]. MRI played a central role in diagnosis, supporting previous research highlighting its diagnostic accuracy in differentiating TB spondylitis from other etiologies [13,18].

A noteworthy finding was the high percentage (50.4%) of cases grouped under “other pathologies,” including multiple sclerosis (MS), arteriovenous malformations (AVMs), spinal cord ischemia, syringomyelia, and spinal cysts. MS was the most frequently identified among these. This trend may

reflect rising awareness and availability of diagnostic imaging for autoimmune and vascular disorders. The increasing recognition of MS aligns with global trends suggesting a broader epidemiological footprint of the disease than previously believed [19].

The comparison between paraplegic and quadriplegic patients revealed no significant differences in etiological distribution, clinical presentation, or demographics. This supports findings by Awan et al., who observed that although the spinal level determines motor deficit severity, the underlying causes are similarly distributed across paraplegia and quadriplegia [20].

Our study reaffirms the value of MRI in evaluating NTCM. MRI with contrast allows for early detection of tumors, infections, degenerative changes, and vascular lesions. For suspected AVMs or ischemia, MR angiography and conventional angiography are essential [9,11,21]. These modalities offer improved accuracy in diagnosis and surgical planning, especially in resource-limited settings.

Limitations of this study include its single-center scope, cross-sectional design, and use of non-probability sampling, which may affect generalizability. Nevertheless, it contributes critical local data on NTCM, an area where literature is scarce in Pakistan.

CONCLUSION

The research emphasizes that non-traumatic compressive myelopathy is characterized by an etiological spectrum in which tumors comprise the most common cause, followed by degenerative and infectious pathology. MRI was imperative to proper diagnosis. There was no significant difference between paraplegic and quadriplegic groups in the etiological distribution, and thus the importance of early imaging and etiological assessment in all patients presenting with non-traumatic spinal cord dysfunction.

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